

The subject of psychology: Seclusion, contraction, immobilisation, objectification, privatisation, and depoliticization*

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Abstract

The seclusion and contraction of subjects in their individualities makes possible their reduction to objects of power apparatuses—of the State, Patriarchy, Capital, and the so-called objective human sciences, including psychology. Nothing is easier than objectifying an individualised, deactivated, and weakened subject who has been plunged into impotence and immobility. It seems that Christianity and capitalist modernity first neutralised subjects, turning them into harmless, isolated individuals, and later objectified them, transmuting them into objects of political, economic, and ideological-scientific systems with psychological devices. The paradox is that psychology developed to support paralysed and powerless individuals, already objectified and neutralised as subjects, in dealing with their emotional, intellectual, or emotional problems. Although such problems are fundamentally political, cultural, or socioeconomic in origin, it is individuals who must take responsibility for them and alleviate them in apolitical ways in their private individual spheres. This depoliticization and privatisation of depression, stress, and anxiety is correlated with the privatisation of all other aspects of our lives in neoliberal capitalist societies. Finally, the possibility is considered that psychology is transformed so radically that it reverses the psychologising process that engenders it: the process of individualisation, contraction, objectification, and depoliticisation of subjectivity.

Keywords

psychology, subjectivity, objectivity, capitalism, neoliberalism

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Individuality as the prison of the subject

There was a time when the protagonists of human history were hordes, clans, tribes, communities, and peoples. These groups embodied humanity. Human subjects were collective rather than locked into individuality. Their problems were primarily group problems, as were the solutions to those problems.

Of course, humans were always individuals, but they recognised themselves as elements of the whole (Tönnies, 1887/2002). They understood that their individual problems were part of a problematic totality that encompassed and internally constituted individuals. The individual subjects knew that they depended on their communities.

Gradually, individuals began to close in on themselves (Swift, 1926). This process lasted for centuries and occurred in parallel in most, but not all, civilisations. In the European context, Christianity partly aided this process from the end of antiquity to the dawn of modernity, passing through the long Middle Ages (see Marx 1843/1987a; Dumont, 1982). Since their appearance in the Western World, Christians always act as individuals when they perform good works, fall into temptation, commit sins, examine their consciences, confess, do penance, and ultimately go to heaven or hell.

What weighs in the balance of the final judgment is the individual soul. Likewise, this soul has weight in modern capitalist societies through individual votes and rights, individual wealth, and individual private ownership. Everything in modernity is centred on the individual soul, which represents humanity and condenses subjectivity.

Modern human subjects, inheritors of Christianity, are imprisoned in their individual souls. These souls are the prisons of their bodies. Consider this well: the body no longer ‘imprisons the soul’, as Plato believed (*Phaedo*, 82d–85b). Instead, as Michel Foucault (1975) stated, the soul has become ‘the prison of the body’ (p. 38). The contradiction between Plato and Foucault reveals a historical mutation. Something has changed between the ancient Greek society and the modern French society of the second half of the 20th century. Foucault inverted Plato to actualise it in a precise historical context.

Contraction, immobilisation, and objectification of the subject

History may have freed the soul, but at the cost of diminishing it to squeeze it through an individual funnel. In Greek antiquity, the great soul of the Athenian free man, overflowing individuality and unfolding in a political space, certainly had reason to feel imprisoned and suffocated in the narrow human body (Constant, 1819/2010). However, over time, the body has increasingly been trapped in a soul narrowed to individuality.

The individual soul continued to shrink and eventually became the object of psychology. This object, in its various psychological, mental, conscious, cognitive, personal, and other forms, results from what Herbert Marcuse (1964/2010) described as an ‘atrophy’, a ‘contraction’ and a ‘lost’ of the internal

world (pp. 102-108). In the tiny, individual, internal worlds in which they have been confined by psychology, subjects are oppressed and crushed, as if buried, and can scarcely move.

Psychological subjects move without moving, turn without doing anything or going anywhere, and agitate without acting, freeing themselves, or transforming their world. The ‘restrictive agency’ offered by psychology (Holzkamp, 1985/2013, pp. 23-26) makes subjects no longer look like subjects (Castro, 2013). Unsurprisingly, they are constructed as the opposite of what they are—as objects of psychology understood as objective science.

Long before the emergence of psychology as an independent objective science, Immanuel Kant (1781/2004, 1786/1971) and others (e.g. Hegel, 1807/1973; Herbart, 1816/1901) criticised the fundamental absurdity of psychological knowledge—its aim of objectifying the subjective, which is the only thing “unobjectifiable” by definition (see Pavón-Cuéllar, 2019a, pp. 17-19). Now, we should ask ourselves how this objectification has become possible. I am convinced that the answer lies in the reduction of subjects to their individual internal worlds.

As Rosa Luxemburg (1905/1985) and György Lukács (1923/1985) have shown, subjects reduced to their individuality are devoid of much that makes them ‘subjects’, not ‘objects’ (see Pavón-Cuéllar, 2017a, pp. 79-80, 83-85). This is the case regarding the capacity for action and transformation of the external sociocultural world. In general, this world can be transformed only by collective subjects, since individual subjects are condemned to ‘contemplate’, passively and resignedly, what they cannot ‘transform’ (see Lukács, 1923/1985, pp. 230-231).

In their powerlessness, contemplative individual subjects are the *objects* of what they cannot transform. For example, individuals cannot end capitalism, but they are usually objects of capitalist exploitation. They are also objects of government oppression, from which they cannot free themselves as individuals. Similarly, whether they are men or women, gay or heterosexual, European or Latin-American, they are objects of the colonial, racist, sexist, and hetero-patriarchal system.

In order not to be simple objects, the subjects should come together and constitute a collective subjectivity. This subjectivity, specifically in the form of a movement founded on a social class, is the only true subjectivity for Luxemburg and Lukács: the only one capable of acting and transforming oppressive systems instead of being the object of them. The tacit teaching of Luxemburg and Lukács is that we can only collectively exercise our subjectivity, while individually we are condemned to be objects of the systems that oppress us.

In Lacanian jargon, *the Big Other*—the way in which the symbolic systems of culture appear to the subject—always finds ways *to enjoy*—to possess and exploit—the individual as its object (see Lacan 1975/1999). An individualised subject is defenceless against the enjoyment of, for example, capital (Exposto & Rodríguez Varela, 2020; Pavón-Cuéllar, 2022). We can only resist such *jouissance* as collective subjects—as ourselves, rather than as insignificant individual *egos* that cannot even preserve the subject condition in the ultimate bastion of individuality.

The seclusion of subjects in their individualities makes it possible to reduce them to objects of power apparatuses—of the State, Patriarchy, Capital, and the so-called objective sciences, including psychology. Nothing is easier than objectifying a subject who is individualised, deactivated, weakened, and plunged into impotence and immobility. It seems that Christianity and capitalist modernity first neutralised subjects, turning them into harmless, isolated individuals, and later objectified them, transmuting them into objects of political, economic, and ideological-scientific systems with psychological devices.

Freedom and subjectivity for capital

The users of psychology are products of the previously summarised story: a long history of individualisation, contraction, immobilisation, and objectification of subjectivity. This history is the same one that has led to neoliberal capitalism (Harvey, 2007; Laval, 2007) in which the psychological perspective, in all its forms, is triumphant (Parker, 2007; De Vos, 2012). The psychology that individualises, contracts, immobilises, and objectifies us is perfectly compatible with a neoliberalism that reduces us to the condition of atomised and isolated individuals, who behave as passive objects of the overarching free market with its wide-ranging movement of commodities (Pavón-Cuéllar, 2017b; Adams et al, 2019).

Neoliberalism can only liberate commodities at the expense of people. The inaugural demand of any neoliberal policy is that we give up our freedom to commodities, the market, and the enjoyment of capital. Capital thus frees itself to freely enjoy neoliberalism. In the current regime of free market and free competition, as in the old free trade criticized by Marx (1848/1987b), the only freedom is the ‘freedom of capital’ (p. 155).

Neoliberal capitalism not only surrenders our freedom to capital but also represents the culmination of a long process by which we transfer our subjectivity to capital itself (see Read, 2009). This capital is the supreme subject of neoliberalism, usurping the place of all other subjects and dominating them, as only the unique divinity did in the most dogmatic and intolerant of religious times. We have become creatures and servants of capital, its fundamentalist and terrorist believers, its crusaders, and its suicide bombers. We give our lives to capital, which can thus enjoy our lives by sucking and absorbing our blood ‘like a vampire’, according to Marx’s (1867/2008, pp. 178-179) famous metaphor in *Das Kapital*.

Individuals as enterprises of capital rather than entrepreneurs of themselves

We are thus faced with a strange situation in which we are the objects of vampirish capital that is the only subject of neoliberal capitalism. We lose sight of this situation when we accept the famous Foucauldian formula of neoliberal

individuals as ‘entrepreneurs of themselves who are their own capital, their own producers, the source of their income’ (Foucault, 1979/2007, pp. 264-265). Foucault’s phrase is quite ambiguous, since it leaves us with the impression that individuals are simultaneously subjects and objects—entrepreneurs and their enterprises—when it is clear that they are only the objects and enterprises *of* something that inhabits and possesses them, i.e. the capital they ‘personify’ (Marx, 1867/2008, p. 178).

Let us recognise, then, that neoliberal individuals are, as Foucault (1979/2007) stated, ‘permanent and multiple enterprises that encompass everything in their lives, including the relationships, for example, with their private property, with their family, with their partner, with their insurance, with their retirement’ (p. 277). This quote by Foucault is revealing because it shows us that the relationship of entrepreneurs with their enterprise is part of the enterprise. In other words, the condition of entrepreneurs, their lives, and their entrepreneurial relationships with themselves is the enterprise of something that must, therefore, transcend individuality (see Brown, 2015).

From a Marxist perspective, neoliberal individuals are not their own entrepreneurs but the enterprise of capital that possesses them and makes them function as their own entrepreneurs. Their actions are the performance of an alien role—the role of capital. Hence, the only subject is capital—the entrepreneur underpinning all entrepreneurs—while the individual is the enterprise—the object exploited by capital and playing the role of entrepreneur, thus personifying capital.

Individuals are the objects of capital exploitation and the capital that they personify, and they suffer directly from the effects of such exploitation, such as by experiencing feelings of emptiness, chronic fatigue, lack of energy or motivation, and depression. Moreover, if individuals are lucid enough and have penetrating Foucauldian sensitivity, they will conclude that their suffering is for all they have exploited themselves as entrepreneurs of themselves. They will thus reproach themselves for demanding too much of themselves, for being work addicts, for not knowing how to rest or enjoy, for not sleeping enough, and for sacrificing what is profoundly important—life, love, pleasure, friendship, and sustenance.

All the reproaches are correct, except for one detail: they address the wrong person. Individuals do not waste their own lives. What ruins the lives of individuals is the capitalist system and the capital that individuals personify, even when they blame themselves. Their reproaches must be included in the list of grievances attributable not to individuals as their own entrepreneurs but to the capital that owns them and that makes them exploit themselves and then blame themselves for their own exploitation.

Blaming ourselves and apologising to capital

I once conversed with a man suffering from terminal cancer who blamed himself for his illness and suffering. This individual sensed that his illness was associated

with certain personality traits. He was extremely serious, industrious, obedient, self-sacrificing, and responsible, to the extent that he took responsibility for his own illness. His words made me think that this desire to take responsibility for everything, including his cancer, was perhaps precisely what had caused the cancer. The problem was that he blamed himself for everything, even the blame itself, and thus took the blame for the system.

Blaming oneself—unloading the guilt of the system on oneself—has become a persistent rule of behaviour since Christianity and later capitalist modernity locked subjects within their individuality. Good Christians who flagellated themselves for their temptations and sinful desires were already taking the blame for Christianity, the prohibitions of which excited their desires and temptations. Christianity then gave way to capitalism—the true universal religion—which has caused tremendous physical and mental suffering in subjects who reproach themselves for their own suffering.

Some patients blame themselves for their diabetes and obesity when advertising has led them to become intoxicated and put on weight by eating fast food and ultra-processed foods with added sugar. Others attribute their cancers solely to their smoking or poor diet, completely forgetting the role of tobacco companies and the factories that poison city air, produce carcinogenic foods, or inundate the agricultural industry with fertilisers and pesticides. Pharmaceutical capital is also often forgotten by its millions of annual victims, who find ways to blame themselves with the help of their doctors.

Psychology as exoneration of the system, depoliticization, and privatisation of cultural discontent

Medicine is usually biased in blaming the sick for their illnesses and exonerating the system that makes them sick. This partiality towards the capitalist system can sometimes be observed in medical practice and occurs regularly in the field of psychology, which is inclined to presume the innocence of the system. Indeed, psychologists tend to deflect attention from capitalism, absolving it completely through the guiding principle that individuals are responsible for their problems and must solve them with the support of professionals.

For example, a cognitive-behavioural therapist can help individuals solve their problems of anxiety, stress, or depression by offering treatment that includes reinforcing certain behavioural patterns, programming for progressive activities, training in problem-solving, and supporting the development of useful skills for coping with stressful situations. The ultimate purpose of this therapy is to encourage individuals to think positively and release the negative thoughts, feelings, and behaviours that feed anxiety, stress, and depression. The assumption is that anxious, stressed, or depressed conditions result from the ways in which individuals feel, think, and behave. Individuals are to blame.

Individuals are accused of what the capitalist system does to them. In addition to being victims of capitalism, they are revictimized by psychology. They suffer double: because they suffer and because they reproach themselves

for being the cause of their suffering. Their suffering, in fact, can be triple when they are victims of positive psychology, because then they suffer not only because they suffer and because they consider themselves guilty of their suffering, but because the very fact of suffering, because suffering is not good, because people are not allowed to suffer even when the capitalist system torments them by all means (Cederström y Spicer, 2015).

The system is not even seen when it is destroying the world around us through climate change and the devastation of nature. We accuse ourselves of the planetary catastrophe for using straws, for eating meat daily, for travelling frequently by plane, for driving a car several hours a day, or for changing smart phones or computers from time to time. It is true that these practices contribute to the environmental cataclysm, but the fundamental responsibility lies with capitalism, which has created devastating needs to ensure consumption and the profits linked to that consumption. All of this is missed by psychologists who, even when dealing with environmental issues, forget the capitalist environment and focus on the individual (e.g. Clayton et al, 2015; Nielsen et al, 2021). The key is in the individual sphere, although sometimes a little influenced by family and social factors.

Psychologists talk about society in order not to look bad, but the truth is that they do not know what to do with it. Hence, they project it as far away as possible in time and space, where it becomes invisible to them—either in the past, confusing it with the family, or behind the wall of the immediate environment, in the socioeconomic and structural background that supposedly cannot be transformed and to which it is necessary to adapt. Finally, for myopic, amnesiac, individualistic, and presentist psychology, only the present and narrow, private, individual spheres remain, where individuals, assisted by psychologists, manoeuvre.

Psychology, in general, starts from the premise that individuals must cope with their emotional, intellectual, or behavioural problems. Although these problems are fundamentally political, cultural, or socioeconomic in origin, it is individuals who must take responsibility for them and solve them in apolitical ways in their private individual spheres. This ‘depoliticisation’ and ‘privatisation’ of depression, stress, and anxiety, as Mark Fischer (2011) claimed, is correlated with the privatisation of all other aspects of our lives under neoliberal capitalism. It can be said that neoliberalism not only privatises culture but also cultural discontent and multiple sufferings in an increasingly privatised culture, progressively subsumed in capitalism.

Cope better with the world, or fight for a better world?

In almost all cultural spheres, the individual must solve the problems caused by the enjoyment of capital. Although capital enjoys, individuals pay the bill. This new form of exploitation, which is an extension of economic exploitation in the classical sense, requires psychology to justify itself by holding subjects responsible for their problems.

From a perspective of positive psychology and cognitive-behavioural models, for example, individuals are fundamentally depressed because of negative thinking (e.g. Teasdale, 1983; Norem & Chang, 2002). This thinking is the important thing. Positive and cognitive-behavioural psychologists rarely show interest in the structural causes of their patients' negative thinking, such as the negative reality in which they live, the cultural misery that surrounds them, life imprisonment in their individual prisons, their exploitation as workers and consumers, or their degrading conditions as objects of the enjoyment of capital.

There is enough evidence that capitalism and neoliberalism cause a variety of mental health problems, including depression and anxiety (Prins et al, 2015; Eisenberg-Guyot & Prins, 2022). This is understandable (see Mathews, 2019; Zeira, 2022). The capitalist system is quite depressing. How can we avoid becoming depressed in this world turned into a market in which increasingly interested relationships prevail? This world is becoming increasingly unstable, insecure, and troubling. How can we not be stressed and anxious in the face of neoliberalism, with its progressive acceleration, law of the jungle, job insecurity, accumulating debt, and ultimate devastation of the planet?

Of course, distressing problems and stressful situations interest cognitive-behavioural psychologists, who respond by offering training in problem-solving and the development of useful skills for dealing with stressful situations. However, what we learn in cognitive-behavioural psychology is to be skilled at dealing with stressful situations—not to be skilful in overcoming these situations when confronted by the neoliberalism that creates them. Similarly, we are not trained to escape the troubled capitalist system, but only to solve the distressing problems it causes.

Cognitive-behavioural psychologists, like almost any other type of psychologist, may justify themselves with the quite reasonable argument that they can only help individuals to deal with the world, but not to change it, since individuals cannot change the world. The most that psychology can offer individuals is change in their relationships with the world—change that makes the world less distressing, stressful, and depressing for them. The point here is that individuals who are less depressed, stressed, and distressed by the world have less reason to want to change that world.

Why do we participate in collective action to try to transform society when we can simply ask psychologists to transform our perceptions of society and our attitude towards it? Is it not easier and faster to seek psychologists to help free us from our negative thinking than to create a revolution to free ourselves from negative reality? The answer is yes: in this case, as in others, curing a disease is slower, more difficult, and more uncertain than alleviating its symptoms.

The problem with simply relieving symptoms is that the alleviation does not cure the disease. Instead, it allows the disease to progress. Capitalism thus continues to gain ground at the expense of humanity and nature. In the last 50 years, during the neoliberal phase of the capitalist system, we have not only witnessed the precariousness of our existence and the worsening of inequalities but also the disappearance of more than half the fertile land and animal populations on our planet (Kolbert, 2014; Ceballos et al, 2017).

Something better than psychology?

We are losing our planet, thus endangering our very existence as humans. This capitalist terminal illness can only be avoided if we escape from the narrow individual prisons in which we have been locked and snatch our subjectivity away from capital. We must stop being objects of capital and its devices, including psychology, and become collective subjects who can fight against capital through social movements and political organisations.

We need to recover the political, social, and subjective selves that are lost when we are psychologised. This requires us to leave behind the individual, apolitical objects of psychological science, and re-subjectify ourselves and re-collectivize our subjectivity through formations such as communist camaraderie, feminist sisterhood, and even religious brotherhood understood in a progressive and anti-capitalist sense, as in certain forms of Liberation Theology. The question is whether all this should make us abandon psychology for good.

Perhaps psychology is capable of transforming itself so radically that it reverses the psychologising process that engenders it: the process of individualisation, contraction, objectification, and depoliticisation of subjectivity. Maybe psychology will find a way to reconstitute collective and political subjects—the only subjects capable of opposing capital. This possibility has already been partially realised by critical, radical, and liberation psychologies, as well as by certain political and community psychological proposals, revealing that psychology need not necessarily be condemned as a capitalist device (see Parker, 2015; Pavón-Cuéllar, 2017c, 2019b).

Capitalism has been repeatedly challenged by psychology. The psychological field is a battlefield: it is a field not only for the domination of capitalism, but also for the struggle against capital. Although the field—as we have tried to show in this article—is not neutral and is already predetermined in some way in favour of the capitalist system, this does not exclude the possibilities of resistance and even subversion.

Past experiences teach us that capitalism loses control over those psychological proposals that commit themselves to collective and political anti-capitalist projects or movements. This external anchorage is essential. Psychology must come out of itself and must also collectivize and politicize itself to be able to escape capitalism and reconstitute collective and political subjects.

In fact, psychology has the potential to be an important ally of anti-capitalist movements and become less psychology than something better (e.g.; Parker, 2020; Parker & Pavón-Cuéllar, 2021; Malherbe, 2022). We clearly need something better than psychology (Parker, 2007). It does not matter if we continue to call it ‘psychology’, but it can no longer be what it has been until now.

Psychology should be deconstructed and rebuilt as something better (Parker, 2014). Only something better can help us to return to being the groups, communities, and peoples that we once were and that we can still be today when we act collectively to change our destinies. We can be something other than the

subject of psychology. We don't deserve its seclusion, contraction, immobilisation, objectification, privatisation, and depoliticization.

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